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A cognitive stage-experiential psycho-educational guidance model to enhance the *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in diversity) awareness

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Abstract:

This research is aimed at describing the need of guidance and counseling model in terms of Cognitive Stage-Experiential Psychoeducation which consisted of books, interactive media, and teacher guidance to be implemented in Primary School. Such service was a classic effort to develop early awareness of the *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in Diversity) for primary school students in East Java. This was a survey research with 120 respondents from 4 towns in East Java. The data were collected through interview and questionnaires. The results of this research show that according to teachers, character education on the awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in diversity) must have been given to students in early stage. Most of the respondents believed that there must be a model to enhance the awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in Diversity) and there have been needs of the development of guidance and counselling media and model for enhancing the character education especially the awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* (Unity in Diversity)

Key Words:

Counselling and Guidance Service, Awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika*, and *Cognitive Stage-Experiential Model*

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Mostly guidance and counselling services in primary schools have been done by teachers. They were familiarized with special experience in terms of guidance and counselling competence in primary schools. They need to be professional in doing their assignment for optimum results. Therefore, they need to have proper guidance and counselling media and model for primary schools.

Bhineka tunggal ika (Unity in Diversity) is a realism of the Indonesian nation that has become one of the nation pillars and foundation of the high civilization. *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* is the terminology that unites a big nation to become one unity by maintaining the original power of each element accumulated to be the great power of one nation. Multiculturalism has been the manifestation of the *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* that cannot be separated from the commitment and the strong interconnection of the Indonesian nation. The awareness on the importance of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* is therefore to be maintained and to become the strong spirit and power of the Indonesian nation.

Bhineka Tunggal Ika concept has been formed and successfully tested since the era of preceding the independence of Indonesia Republic and has also been examined in the early period of independence. The psychological source of nationality encouraging the formation of the big power for eliminating colonialist has been the unity from the diversity of the Indonesian Nation. This has been formulized by the differences of tribes and geographical areas stretching away from Sabang to Merauke and from Nias island to Rote Island. The ethnical differences and nature of origin finally form a cultural diversity.

The cultural differences have become important phenomena and concerns for the life of our school children including those who are in early age. The cultural diversity and differences of school children at school happen due to several causes, such as the population distribution, parents occupation, or origin of the places they visited for pursuing their studies. The students diversity consists of ethnical differences and diversity, gender, cultural background, original geographical area, race, age physical condition (Sue,1991) as well as differences and diversity in socio economical status, religion, personal characteristics, social ability, behavior, custom and habit, and intellectual ability.

In the Indonesian context, cultural diversity has been a natural phenomena due to the interconnection of various local culture and the fact that every individual coming from different cultural ethnic and tribe bring with them with their specific way of life. Multicultural concept is different from crosscultural concept such as that of which is experienced by American due to incoming various cultures that bind into a nation. In the *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* concept, individual differences cover a broad meaning; Meanwhile, in the cross cultural concept the focus has been on the ethnical differences.

Students from the early stage of their life must learn how to respect the existence of group, original tribes, and religion existing across the country. Factually, it cannot be rejected that there has been natural trend to form groups which meet their expectation freely. Such factual trend also has been flowerized by online and electronic media that make children (event those who are in the early stage) to become parts of unlimited world. The incoming animated movie from overseas make children have global experience. Nobody can blame children doing mistakes when they know NINJA HATORI more than their own friends in other parts of Indonesia as the member of nation family. There has always reason of their social learning existence. Such situation often has been caused by the pragmatic attitude of their parents towards any experience coming to their houses through television. With such condition, school must be able to capture and watch the phenomena out in order that the school has created character based as well as awareness of the diversity learning strategy.

In this research, the researchers place the awareness of the diversity and *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* on the important position and event these have the same importance as the students' academic achievement. Such awareness is formulized in the mind of school children in order that they enlarge their positive thinking and action by paying attention to cultural aspects. This must become the source of inspiration to strengthen their community.

Based on the importance of developing *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* awareness with the complexity and strong challenges of the educator duties to pay attention to various aspects of learning, it is highly needed to develop psychoeducational strategy enabling students to have proportional attention in their groups maximally. The above statements imply that (1) educational program must cover cognitive, emotional, and actional aspects, and (2) psychoeducational model to cover these three aspects is highly needed, (3) the researchers offer a psychoeducational model named *Cognitive Stage-Experiential* to enhance the early awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika*.

Early awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* is the attainment of cognitive development showing understanding, knowledge, and high commitment of the fact that Indonesian nation comprises various tribes, groups of origin with various habits and cultures that create cultural diversity. These awareness and commitment to form the big strong united nation require the students' understanding on the importance of making togetherness to attain the main goal of the Indonesian nation. *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* is then believed to be existing and understood, as well as highly respected.

Sue dan Sue, 2003, (in akhmadi, 2012) describes the model of multicultural multidimensional competence which is integrated with three characteristics of the *Bhineka Tunggal Ika*, which are the need to concern the view of specific cultural group related with race, gender, sexual orientation, and other cultural aspects. Multicultural components cover differences of specific culture related to race, gender, sexual orientation, and other cultural aspects. This model initially only identified five big groups of race, in the long run this model also covered socio economy, religion, and other differences.

Multicultural awareness according to Ingran (2001), as stated by Akhmadi (2012), is an individual who understand, comprehend, and respect how culture becomes specific characteristics and lead personal action, the ability to acknowledge more differences as diversity than abnormal behavior or improper respond. *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* awareness is the ability to acknowledge various cultural differences and similarities and the ability to view differences as diversity (Locke, 1992; Waak & Donogian, 2004; Akhmadi, 2012).

Models can be defined as: (1) the representation of a concept or system which can be a diagram of two or three dimensions, mathematical diagrams or other analogies, (2) the means to transfer the relationship or actual the background into something that makes it easy to learn (Thomas, & Marshall, 1978). Model is also meant as a plan that is used as a guide to carry out an activity (Joyce & Weil, 1980). Shertzer and Stone (1981) states that model refers to the representation of abstraction of a final product due to the values inherent in it. While Richey (1986) explains that in application, model implies the sense of a reality that is represented in the form of the level, structure and composition.

On the basis of the above notions, model can be defined as a simplified representation of structured and organized reality to make it more easily to understand. Simplified elements are detailed, structured, plotted, scaled and ordered. Representation of reality can be presented in the physical and non-physical forms. Representation of reality in the physical form means that which can be observed directly (Harre in Richey, 1986) as flowchart, used drawings scale, organ in the human body globe. On the other hand, the representation of reality in non-physical form appears in some form that was created.

One of the models, according to Harre (dalam Richey, 1986) is a procedural model. The procedural model simplify complex process and interaction in understandable orders and Procedural model shows steps followed in doing problem solving (Richey,1986).

Psychoeducation model is a set of efforts and systematic measures that include components of the methods and techniques as the process of changing the behavior and personality of the specific component in order to better enhancement to achieve optimal development. Psychoeducation model was being developed and tested through this research and become the manifestations of the presence of vast opportunities, in which the principles and processes were combined with experiential learning stage of cognitive development. The model offered as experiential learning model can be packed into a combined educational program development and behavior as well as specific personality components by following psychological principles. Such design, in other term, can be said as the application of micro to macro techniques (Prawitasari, 2011). Furthermore, Prawitasari (2011) explains that the application of therapeutic techniques (micro) in the macro program must be accompanied by an effort, in which psychologists have to learn through improvement programs. In practice, psychoeducation utilizes more techniques and methods of psychotherapy and learning to serve as a basic foundation taking systematic steps. So, this can be concluded that the application of micro-learning techniques and psychotherapy into a macro program is possible. Therefore, psychologists and teachers can develop a preventive program procedures as a package in a model of psychoeducation. On this occasion, the authors offer a package of preventive measures in psychoeducation program named Cognitive Stage-experiential models.

Application of Cognitive Stage development theory of William Perry (1999) and Experiential learning theory of David Kolb (1984) in the process of psychoeducation can be combined as a model of effective psycho-education to raise awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* for early primary school students. Symptoms were often found in the field, primary school students still had provisions mind that they were different from others because of the different family economic background. Many of them gathered and enhanced group cohesiveness on the basis of similarity consideration and family background. In contrast, they saw that another group had lower family economic background was seen as an external group. Conversely, many among those who gathered on the basis of the economic background of the same family, in the sense that they departed from the lower middle economy was not entitled or awkward to follow the footsteps of their friends who came from upper middle class family background. Both those who considered themselves as high and low have a tendency to have dualism, dichotomous and unwarranted attitude. Other aspects as a source of cultural differences such as race, gender, national origin were related. In such condition, the cognitive development of students according to Perry (1999) was still in a low level of cognitive development that has been called dualism.

Psychoeducation process should be to improve the cognitive development of students to a higher level of development, that is multiplicity-relativism to commitment. In looking at differences in a background of which is often a source of cultural differences of students, teachers should be able to create a situation that allows the process of reflection by using the experiences (both natural and by designed), abstracting the process of internalization and abstract concepts of early awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* to do experiments in the form of improved concept of reciprocal social relations among students from different cultures. Therefore, the theory of Kolb's experiential learning can be used through a merger with the format of cognitive developmental stages according to Perry .

The problem of research are then described as the psychoeducation model of cognitive stage-experiential needed worth at helping develop an early awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* for primary school students?.

Keterangan:

CE: *Concrete Experience (Feeling)*

RO: *Reflective Observation (Watching)*

AC: *Abstract Conceptualization (Thinking)*

AE: *Active Experimentation (Doing)*

Graphic 1.3: Psychoeducational Model of Cognitive Stage-experiential from researcher

METHOD

Psychoeducation models of developed Cognitive Stage-Experiential was a model of psychoeducation which was included into the scope of educational activities. Therefore: (1) the development model was following the model of the software development in the field of education in general, as noted by some experts (Borg & Gall, 1983; Dick & Carey, 1987; Gustavson, 1981; and with regard implementation measures of Experiential learning (Kolb, 1984; Cook & Olson, 2006); (2) The procedure to be performed in the development of psychoeducation model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential have similar characteristics with the development model of instructional systems of Dick & Carey; namely (a) action-oriented products development in the form of a psychoeducation model Experiential Cognitive Stage, (b) development activity done either individually or as a group, (c) emphasis on the development or selection of materials, and (d) through the repeated trials.

The following steps were prepared: Preparation of initial model prototype, designing and producing valid and reliable treatment instruments and testing the treatment instruments carefully. This study took two categories of instrument treatment, which were the treatment instrument for actual treatment and the instruments of treatment for sample prior to treatment using the actual treatment instrument. There were two alternative instruments developed.

Each of these alternative treatment instrument packages was a tangible Cognitive Stage-Experiential model equipped with software (software). This software messaged experience as the main character of the model for Cognitive Stage-Experiential. The Instruments were developed, used and tested by the researchers. The researchers adapted from the tracking sources of raw input which was better than youtube, such as vents which were broadcasted by television and online media.

Instrument validation of the model in question was a set list of questions, statements and cartridge containing the material elements model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential. These instruments were intended to facilitate the validation team (matter experts, media experts and the participants) made an assessment to see whether the

response element model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential already fit, psychologically communicative accordance with the rules, and followed the rules of multi-media and pull-communicative measure. Instrument validation of the model was made in three sets, each of which differs according to the assessors. Practically, the instrument validation package included a model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential and assessed by an expert (expert) after seeing the package model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential. The materials expert group received 1 (one) set package models Cognitive Stage-Experiential covering model scenarios Cognitive Stage-Experiential, while the group of media experts and a sample users group only receive one set package design of organizations messaging experience in the form of video recordings, audio, image and text has been designed and is a single unit or integrated.

In terms of the goal of this research to develop products such as models of Cognitive Stage-Experiential to raise early students' awareness of Bhineka Tunggal Ika. Therefore, the instrument of validation product was a set list of statements, questions, and impressions that measure variables implementation Stage Cognitive-Experiential models as independent variables. The application of the model Cognitive Stage-Experiential was measured to see how far the model package Cognitive-Stage Experiential could be applied in the intervention program in accordance to the principles and techniques in the model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential. Products in the form of models or treatment devices that had been developed by the researchers prior to be tested in the field, they were consulted to the media experts, and the experts for the field of study (psychology and counseling). Then, revision was done in accordance to the results of the consultation and testing. These activities were intended to be produced by the software developer in accordance to the conditions established for use as a treatment instrument. Implementation of field trials involved three groups of samples that produced validation test samples developed for the materials studied by the group of experts, media experts, and users. This trial was done by providing a data collection instrument to the media experts, a field of study and users. Data collection instruments were given in the form of validation of instruments developed and prepared beforehand.

The model was developed by the following stages (1) describe the content of the material model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential, (2) describe the contents of indicators, (3) outline a grain stuffing based on the map contents model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential, (4) the translation of the grains stuffing was tested rationally according to the expert judgment the content of the materials and empirically tested in the field to determine whether the prepared questionnaires could be understood by the assessors, (5) make revisions or cancellation of grain fields in accordance to the stipulated requirements.

Early awareness of Bhineka Tunggal Ika was measured to see how far these variables change increased. To measure early awareness of Bhineka Tunggal Ika, the researchers developed non-test instrument in term of a psychological scale (awareness of Bhineka Tunggal Ika scale).

Early awareness of Bhineka Tunggal Ika Scale developed by the following steps (1) describe Bhineka Tunggal Ika variables as indicators of early awareness,(2) described the indicators into descriptors, (3) described the descriptors items into statements, questions in terms of both a psychological scale, (4) the translation item grain field was tested rationally according to expert judgment on the content of the materials and were empirically validated in the field to determine the validity and reliability of psychological scale (5) revised or cancelled the grain fields in accordance with the requirements that had been established, (6) finalized scale of early awareness of Bhineka Tunggal Ika.

The main objective was to carry out validation manifest information describing the feasibility level model of Cognitive Stage-Experiential. The extent of Cognitive Stage-Experiential model could be applied. In addition, validation may have also been directed to look at the reliability and validity of a psychological scale used to measure students' early awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika*. Therefore, the subjects of model validation for the Cognitive Stage-experiential were students and teachers of primary schools taken from five regions that represented characteristics of students in East Java. In each region, this research took 6 primary school teachers and 10 students. Students were into the sample testing, in addition they assess the products are being validated is also subject to those instruments collecting data early awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika*.

The data to be collected included (a) the feasibility of the model which included the design, procedures, structure, purpose and content of a model psychoeducation Cognitive Stage-Experiential given by experts, (b) the data feasibility model that contained, among others: suitability, the attractiveness of the subject teachers and students of low grade primary school, (c) data on the results of the test instrument collecting data early awareness *kebhinekatunggalikaan* (about Unity in Diversity) to be analyzed regarding the validity and reliability, and (d) data on the effectiveness of the psychoeducation model of cognitive stage-experiential from the test results from limited field of students.

The analyzed data was the data that contained the expert assessment of scores evaluation and suggestions for improvements and were analyzed by using descriptive and qualitative data analysis. Data from teachers and students about the feasibility of the model were analyzed by using qualitative and descriptive analysis techniques. Data on the test results of data collection instruments were analyzed by using alpha reliability analysis techniques, the validity of the instrument were analyzed by using factor analysis. While testing, the effectiveness of the data were analyzed by using different test (t-student).

RESULT

Book study is a set of activities that aimed to find a theoretical clarity about the object that was being discussed as Cognitive Stage-Experiential of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* awareness. In this case the researchers had given a full explanation on the theory or literature review, and gives a brief study and practical implementation of the guidelines set forth in the form of psychoeducation models Cognitive Stage-Experiential that complete included as an attachment.

Needs analysis was conducted in order to explore how much the teachers and students in need of the models that were being developed. This needs analysis was preceded by the preparation activities instrument and data collection from primary sources, better known as the needs assessment process. Need assessment conducted by asking a number of questions to the user which results user as a material consideration in determining the prototype and reference models. Therefore, need assessment done previously was performed in accordance with the design specifications of the products that had been planned. Furthermore, the results of need assessment could be presented in the next description.

Needs assessment results were taken from the proposed development of 16 factors that had been analyzed as presented on table 1 that reflected the performance of teachers about the possibility to apply 16 factors considered as applicable techniques. In addition to the need assessment as a result of what being described above, the researchers did the needs assessment study more specialized and involved characteristic of models to be developed. Results of the need assessment covering 16 next questions was presented in the following table.

Label: 1 Data of need assesment

No.	QUESTION	ANSWER	
		YES	NO
01.	Is character education in particular of Bhineka Tunggal Ika awareness of for students need to be implemented at an early age?	120	-
02.	Is character education in particular awareness of Bhineka Tunggal Ika that have been implemented in schools have adequate?	60	60
03.	Do understanding of the ethnic diversity of Indonesia (Bhineka Tunggal Ika) will be given to students at an early age?	120	-
04.	Does every teacher has sufficient experience of the diversity of cultural, ethnic and racial in Indonesia?	60	60
05.	Does every teacher has given enough experience about Bhineka Tunggal Ika?	70	50
06.	Is character education in particular "hinekatunggalika" awareness require special media that support?	65	55
07.	Is character education in particular Bhineka Tunggal Ika awareness require special models that support	80	40
08.	Whether the teacher has been reflecting on the facts as evidence concrete ethnic diversity in Indonesia?	50	70
09.	Do teachers have reflect any adverse event due to lack of awareness of the cultural diversity of Indonesia?	70	50
10.	Do you think the need to develop a good learning model for character education in particular kebhinnekatunggalikaan awareness?	120	-
11.	Do you think the media need to develop a good learning for character education in particular Bhineka Tunggal Ika awareness?	90	30
12.	Apakah di sekolah anda telah tersedia model pendidikan karakter khususnya kesadaran kebhinnekatunggalikaan yang baik? Does your school have provided a model of character education particularly good Bhineka Tunggal Ika awareness?	60	60
13.	Does your school have available educational good media, especially the character of awareness Bhineka Tunggal Ika?	70	50
14.	Whether the teacher has to reflect the diversity of ethnic groups in Indonesia?	100	20
15.	Whether the teacher has used the medium of television for character education in particular awareness of the diversity of ethnic groups in Indonesia?	80	40
16.	Do you have designed wake particular character education of Bhineka Tunggal Ika awareness media?	-	120

After validation analisis there are several principles that should be filled. Layout and arrangement of the order/ building information for the child must be accompanied by a more concrete illustration of that information more widely. Automatic type of information is more diverse, illustration description richer information and the type of tasks that there are more attractive in terms presentation.

Memory and internalization of the information presented should be tied. The bond can be a matter of exposure, tasks or activities that could be termed a "bridge of memory". Bridge of memory needed to make a memory that has been entered into the next child's understanding and diakualisasi retained and internalized into the personality structure.

DISCUSSION

The results of need assessment were (1) Teachers had not been doing character education, especially regarding early awareness of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika*. (2) Education characters of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* awareness especially for students needed to be implemented at an early age. (3) An understanding of the diversity of the peoples of Indonesia (*Bhineka Tunggal Ika*) should have been given to students from an early age. (4) Education, especially the character of *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* awareness required special supporting models. (5) Teachers did not reflect the facts as evidence of concrete ethnic diversity in Indonesia. (6) According to the teachers, there needed to develop a good learning model for character education in particular concerning *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* awareness. (7) Teachers had not designed a particular character education media for awaking the *Bhineka Tunggal Ika* awareness.

The emotional experience of each individual at this time would affect the pattern of emotional reactions and physiological actions. Was an emotional reaction to a culture based on rules that had been standardized and mutually recognized as values and cultural norms, or was against the rules of the culture? Both of which followed the basic values and cultural norms and against impact and reactions were certainly different. These became a different emotional experience. Therefore, the processes of reflection and reflection of real object on other events became materials for the reconstruction of the formation of new experiences, and these were referred to as a process designed as a better experience. The teacher's task was to accompany the participants to be able to function in the reconstruction of the current experience less favorable into a new experience that was highly beneficial for all parties.

In the system-component approach, Mascolo, Harkins, and Harakal, 2000 (in Holodynski Manfred, Wolfgang F and Jonathan H 2006) makes the concept of emotional development in the open model even more. Their theory offers three basic assumptions: (1) emotional state (which refers to a complete emotional episode) and emotional experience (which refers to aspects of the phenomenon of emotional state) contains some of the various components (multiple component processes). They consider the element of interpretation of the relevant assessment as to the motive; as well as a system that affect the product such as the SSP, ANS, and the body's reaction that produces the tone and feeling of open action consisting of facial and vocal reaction spontaneity and voluntary action, (2) developing an emotional experience through joint arrangements with system-component from time to time and in a particular social context, (3) System is a component of context sensitivity, ie, not just their own tailor with others, but also to changes in the social context continuously.

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